

ISic3398

I.Sicily inscription 3398

Language

Latin

Type

building (?)

Material

sandstone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

area of the north-south portico in the area of the imperial forum

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico

Regionale di Centuripe, inventory KA857 + KA860

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 645616

Bibliography

Libertini, G 1926. Centuripe. Catania. At 44

Patané, R. P. A. 2011. Impero di Roma e passato troiano nella società del II secolo. Il punto di vista di una famiglia di Centuripe. Rome. At 47 fig.36

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